

Synthesis, Spectral, Thermal, Electrical and Antimicrobial Studies of some Complexes derived from 7-(α -Phenyl- α -*m/p*-nitroanilinomethyl)-8-quinolinol

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Metal complexes of 7-(α -phenyl- α -*m/p*-nitroanilinomethyl)-8-quinolinol (PMNAMQ/PPNAMQ) with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO^{VI} have been prepared and characterised. They have also been tested for their antimicrobial activities.

Mannich bases assumed new importance because of their antibacterial and antifungal activities¹. A simple but interesting Mannich type reaction occurs with aromatic amine, benzaldehyde and 8-quinolinol giving the biologically active 7-substituted-8-quinolinols. Several workers extended this reaction to different aromatic and heterocyclic amines and aldehyde to obtain potential drugs² and analytical reagents³. Several complexes of Ni^I, Co^I, Cu^{II}, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} with Mannich bases have been studied⁴.

The present communication reports Mannich bases 7-(α -phenyl- α -*m*-nitroanilinomethyl)-8-quinolinol (PMNAMQ) and 7-(α -phenyl- α -*p*-nitroanilinomethyl)-8-quinolinol (PPNAMQ) and also their complexes with Cu^{II}, Ni^I, Co^{II}, Zn^I, Mn^{II}, Hg^I, Cd^{II} and UO^{VI} metal ions. The PMNAMQ and PPNAMQ Mannich bases and their metal chelates have been tested for their antimicrobial properties. The structure of the complexes has been established using analytical, thermal, magnetic moment, ir and electronic spectral data.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the metal chelates are presented in Table 1. Elemental analyses of the complexes indicate 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry.

Magnetic and reflectance spectra : The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} complex (1.7–1.8 B.M.) indicates

square-planar geometry. The reflectance spectra show two bands at 14 285–14 310 and 25 316–25 641 cm⁻¹. The former band assigned to ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} transition, is in the range generally observed for planar Cu^I complexes. The latter band is ligand-metal charge transfer transition⁵. The Ni^{II} complexes showing magnetic moment of 2.95–3.00 B.M., is close to the range required for octahedral stereochemistry. The reflectance spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 9 352–9 225, 15 566–16 635 and 23 499–23 260 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{2g} (F), ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{1g} (F) and ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{1g} (P) transitions respectively, considering an octahedral symmetry. The structure is further confirmed by the ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.67–1.69) close to the value expected for octahedral structure⁶. The Co^{II} complexes having magnetic moment of 3.92–4.13 B.M., is in the expected range for a tetrahedral geometry¹⁰. The reflectance spectra of the Co^I complexes exhibit three bands at 8 996–8 905, 16 399–16 065 and 24 680–23 880 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁(F), ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁(P) and charge transfer transitions respectively, considering a tetrahedral geometry⁷.

The magnetic moment of the Mn^I complexes (5.46–5.41 B.M.) is lower than the spin-only value which may be due to partial aerial oxidation of Mn^I to Mn^{II} during synthesis. Its reflectance spectra exhibit bands at 12 820–12 850, 15 873–15 885 and 23 809–23 825 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to the ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF IIR COMPLEXES

Compd. / (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Cacl.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	σ cm ⁻¹	E_1 eV
	M	C	H	N			
PMNAMQ (Yellow)	-	71.17 (71.20)	4.52 4.60	11.21 11.30)	-	5.32×10^{14}	0.3280
Cu(PMNA MQ) ₂ (Green)	7.82 (7.90)	65.67 65.70	3.78 3.98	10.38 10.45)	1.63	4.75×10^{13}	0.0866
Ni(PMNA MQ.H ₂ O) ₂ (Brown)	6.98 (7.03)	63.18 63.25	3.66 3.83	9.94 10.06)	2.99	6.7×10^{12}	0.0938
Co(PMNA MQ) ₂ (Brown)	7.29 (7.37)	65.94 66.09	3.88 4.00	10.43 10.51)	4.13	1.16×10^{12}	0.0728
Zn(PMNA MQ) ₂ (Yellow)	8.10 (8.14)	65.51 65.54	3.91 3.97	10.40 10.43)	Diamag.	1.69×10^{12}	0.1320
Mn(PMNA MQ.H ₂ O) ₂ (Brown)	6.57 (6.61)	63.39 63.54	3.68 3.85	9.96 10.10)	5.45	2.63×10^{13}	0.0380
Hg(PMNA MQ) ₂ (Yellow)	21.23 (21.33)	55.97 56.13	3.31 3.40	8.81 8.93)	Diamag.	9.49×10^{13}	0.0730
Cd(PMNA MQ) ₂ (Yellow)	13.14 (13.18)	61.68 61.94	3.69 3.75	9.81 9.85)	Diamag.	1.99×10^{12}	0.0630
UO ₂ (PMNA MQ.H ₂ O) ₂ (Red)	25.73 (25.81)	50.32 50.47	2.98 3.06	7.96 8.03)	Diamag.	5.3×10^{13}	0.0592
PPNA MQ (Yellow)	-	71.22 (71.20)	4.51 4.60	11.24 11.32)	-	1.75×10^{12}	0.1850
Cu(PPNA MQ) ₂ (Green)	7.68 (7.90)	65.64 65.70	3.84 3.98	10.35 10.45)	1.80	3.2×10^{13}	0.0892
Ni(PPNA MQ.H ₂ O) ₂ (Brown)	6.99 (7.03)	63.12 63.25	3.79 3.83	9.89 10.06)	2.95	3.05×10^{11}	0.0820
Co(PPNA MQ) ₂ (Brown)	7.26 (7.37)	65.89 66.08	3.78 4.00	10.43 10.51)	3.92	2.46×10^{11}	0.0740
Zn(PPNA MQ) ₂ (Yellow)	7.96 (8.14)	65.46 65.54	3.85 3.97	10.21 10.42)	Diamag.	2.55×10^{12}	0.0760
Mn(PPNA MQ.H ₂ O) ₂ (Brown)	6.44 (6.61)	63.36 63.54	3.82 3.85	9.70 10.10)	5.46	2.0×10^{12}	0.0670
Hg(PPNA MQ) ₂ (Yellow)	21.11 (21.32)	56.08 56.13	3.38 3.40	8.80 8.93)	Diamag.	2.78×10^{12}	0.0980
Cd(PPNA MQ) ₂ (Yellow)	13.06 (13.18)	61.73 61.94	3.68 3.75	9.75 9.85)	Diamag.	3.63×10^{12}	0.0430
UO ₂ (PPNA MQ.H ₂ O) ₂ (Red)	25.60 (25.81)	50.33 50.47	2.99 3.05	7.90 8.03)	Diamag.	1.69×10^{12}	0.0960

*(PMNA MQ) = anion of PMNA MQ; (PPNA MQ) = anion of PPNA MQ.

(⁴G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g} (⁴G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_{1g}, ⁴A_{1g} (⁴G) transitions respectively, considering an octahedral symmetry⁸. The reflectance spectra of the UO₂²⁺ chelates exhibit bands at 20 000–20 110 and 26 315–24 314

418 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ¹ε_g⁺ → ³π_u and charge transfer transitions respectively for octahedral stereochemistry⁹. The Zn^{II}, UO₂²⁺, Hg^{II} and Cd^I complexes are diamagnetic.

Infrared spectra : The ir band at $3\ 420\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ of Mannich bases has been assigned to OH bonded to N of 8-quinolinol^{10,11}. This band is absent in the spectra of the metal chelates indicating the removal of H in the complex formation. The broad band at $\sim 3\ 320\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (NH) has been observed in the Mannich bases and their metal complexes^{10,12}. In the spectra of Mannich bases and their metal chelates the three bands observed around $1\ 580$, $1\ 570$ and $1\ 460\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to the presence of heteroatomic compound^{10,13}. A new band of medium intensity in the metal chelates at $\sim 1\ 100$ – $1\ 200\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to C–O–M stretching vibration¹⁴. The ir band at $\sim 1\ 600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=N of 8-quinolinol system)^{10,15} of Mannich bases shifted to $\sim 1\ 630\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the metal chelates indicating the involvement of nitrogen in the chelate formation¹². The new bands at ~ 640 – 630 and ~ 680 – $670\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to M–N and M–O stretch respectively¹². The band at $3\ 350$ – $3\ 370\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} and UO_2^{VI} complexes show the presence of coordinated water molecule¹⁶. Thus it may be concluded that Mannich base acts as monobasic bidentate ligand.

Electrical conductivity : The electrical conductivity of the ligands and their metal chelates was studied over wide range of temperatures. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies exponentially with the absolute temperature according to the relationship,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$$

where σ is the conductivity at T (K), σ_0 the specific conductivity, E_a the activation energy and k is the Boltzmann constant. The activation energy decreases in the order : PMNAMQ > Zn > Ni > Cu > Hg > Co > Cd > UO_2 > Mn and PPNAMQ > Hg > UO_2 > Cu > Ni > Zn > Co > Mn > Cd, which is in partial agreement with the reported results¹⁷.

Thermal study : The TG and DSC studies (Table 2) reveal that metal chelates follow a single step decomposition. From TG traces, it is observed that the rate of decomposition of metal chelates is faster than that of the parent ligand. The Broido method was applied to TG data to determine the energy of activation and

the order of reaction¹⁸. The two water molecules present in the Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} and UO_2^{VI} complexes were lost around 160° , indicating that these molecules are coordinated to the respective metal ion¹⁹. The trend in thermal stability of the metal chelates on the basis of E_a values in decreasing order is as follows : PMNAMQ > UO_2 > Cu > Mn > Co > Zn > Ni > Hg > Cd and PPNAMQ > UO_2 > Zn > Ni > Mn > Hg > Co > Cd.

DSC traces show a single endothermic peak in Mannich bases, which is due to melting transition of Mannich bases. Metal complexes show single exothermic peak in all traces which is due to their crystallisation temperature. The chelates do not undergo any observable physical or chemical change before their thermal decomposition. The loss of two water molecules is noticed by the presence of weak endothermic peak in Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} and UO_2^{VI} traces.

Antimicrobial activities : The ligands PMNAMQ, PPNAMQ and their metal chelates were studied for their antimicrobial behaviour towards *B. subtilis*, *P. fluorescens*, *E. coli*, *S. marcescens*, *A. niger*, *T. longibrachiatum*, *P. stipitis* and *R. minuta*. PMNAMQ and PPNAMQ showed about (60–70%) growth of all the test organisms as compared to control. The Ni, Cd and Hg chelates showed antimicrobial effect on all test organisms. This may be due to inhibitory nature of these metal ions. Metal chelates of Cu, Co, Zn and Mn showed stimulation of growth as compared to the ligands. Remarkable inhibition of *P. fluorescens*, *S. marcescens*, *A. niger* and *T. longibrachiatum* was noticed (50–60%) with Cu and Co chelates of PMNAMQ and PPNAMQ, while Zn, Mn and UO_2 chelates showed moderate growth. The results suggest that variation in structure on coordination affects the growth of microorganisms and may result into either inhibitory effect (antimicrobial), stimulatory effect or reduction in toxicity of metal ions towards some microorganisms.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The Mannich bases PMNAMQ and PPNAMQ were synthesised by the known method³.

TABLE 2—TG AND DSC DATA[†] OF THE LIGAND AND CHELATES

Compd.**	TG					DSC			
	T_S	T_E	Weight loss	E_a	Order of reaction	T_S	T_L	Peak temp.	Jg^{-1}
	°C	°C	%	kcal mol ⁻¹	(n)	°C	°C	°C	
PMNAMQ	125	215	78.5	7.36	1	110	165	145.85	126.50
Cu(PMNAMQ) ₂	295	345	67.9	6.97	1	275	330	323.70	62.0
Ni(PMNAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	190	280	75.0	5.58	1	175	255	337.30	87.41
Co(PMNAMQ) ₂	205	280	60.2	6.11	1	180	250	230.0	280.0
Zn(PMNAMQ) ₂	290	310	68.3	5.79	1	285	330	315.0	193.20
Mn(PMNAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	230	350	75.0	6.41	1	240	315	309.77	166.90
Hg(PMNAMQ) ₂	265	295	57.0	5.19	1	250	260	249.0	34.50
Cd(PMNAMQ) ₂	275	395	73.8	4.86	1	280	345	322.0	87.0
UO ₂ (PMNAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	205	290	70.4	7.29	1	180	255	236.60	87.45
PPNAMQ	215	295	78.3	7.59	1	200	275	238.99	62.07
Cu(PPNAMQ) ₂	265	310	60.8	5.36	1	280	330	322.76	49.90
Ni(PPNAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	210	285	68.2	4.66	1	175	260	236.53	87.40
Co(PPNAMQ) ₂	235	305	57.4	4.52	1	220	265	248.03	109.80
Zn(PPNAMQ) ₂	250	327	74.0	6.49	1	260	325	309.77	196.70
Mn(PPNAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	190	310	72.8	5.19	1	175	265	236.50	106.50
Hg(PPNAMQ) ₂	255	280	52.7	4.89	1	245	265	248.48	34.42
Cd(PPNAMQ) ₂	280	345	55.4	4.29	1	265	315	321.40	55.45
UO ₂ (PPNAMQ.H ₂ O) ₂	265	330	73.8	6.67	1	250	310	310.0	166.90

T_S = Starting temp.; T_E = ending temp.

** (PMNAMQ) = anion of PMNAMQ; (PPNAMQ) = anion of PPNAMQ.

Ni^{II} complexes : Ni^{II}-acetate monohydrate (0.005 mol) dissolved in DMF (~50 ml) was added to Mannich base PMNAMQ (0.01 mol, 3.71 g) dissolved in DMF (~100 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h. The resulting solid was washed with hot distilled water and DMF and dried in an oven at 60°. (3.5–4.0 g). The metal complexes of PMNAMQ and PPNAMQ Mannich bases were synthesised by the same method. All the complexes were found insoluble in common organic solvents.

C, H and N were analysed on a Carlo-Erba analyser. Metals were analysed by standard procedure²⁰. Magnetic studies were made at room temperature by the Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobalt(II) as a calibrant. Reflectance spectra were scanned on a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer using MgO as a reference material and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer. Thermal studies were

done on a Du-Pont 951 thermal analyser. DSC data were obtained on a general V2-2A Du-Point 9900 analyser. Electrical conductivity was measured over a wide range of temperature in air using a Hewlett-Packard 4329-A high resistance meter.

Pre-grown cultures of bacteria, yeast and fungi were inoculated into nutrient broth (N.broth) MGYB and czapek medium respectively. The activities of bacteria and yeast were estimated by measuring growth after 48 and 96 h respectively, using a Systronic spectrophotometer at 660 nm. The experiment was carried out with and without sample (500 ppm). Activities of fungi on sample (750 ppm) were determined by measuring growth after 96 h. The growth was determined as dry cell mass.

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